

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA FOR CAESAREAN SECTION IN A PATIENT WITH BASILAR ARTERY ANEURYSM – CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Pregnancy complicated by the diagnosis of intracranial aneurysm is an example of high-risk pregnancy where maternal and fetal mortality caused by rupture of the aneurysm is 5-12% compared to mortality in the general population which is 0.01-0.09%. The main feature is accidental detection due to non-specific resistant headaches. In this case report we discuss the anesthetic management for cesarean delivery of a parturient with an unruptured aneurysm. The anesthetic technique of choice was epidural anesthesia, L3-L4 level and administration of local anesthetic - levobupivacaine 0.5% with opioid adjuvant - fentanyl. The relationship between the mode of delivery and risk for aneurysm rupture is not well defined.

The decision on anesthetic management is significantly influenced by the physiological changes of pregnancy because they increase the risk of aneurysm rupture as a result of sudden changes in intracranial pressure. Hemodynamic stability is crucial for safe and secure anesthesia and controlling the risk of aneurysm rupture.

Keywords: Unruptured basilar artery aneurysm, parturient, epidural anesthesia, caesarean section

INTRODUCTION

High-risk pregnancies are a significant problem and a challenge for both gynecologists – obstetricians and anesthesiologists because they require a multidisciplinary approach. They are characterized by an increased risk of possible complications and a significant degree of morbidity and mortality.

Pregnancy complicated by the diagnosis of intracranial aneurysm is an example of high-risk pregnancy where maternal and fetal mortality caused by rupture of the aneurysm is 5-12% compared to mortality in the general population which is 0.01-0.09%. (1) The female sex is a significant independent predictor of the formation and growth of aneurysms. According to the International Study of Unruptured Intracranial Aneurysms of 4060 examined patients with 75% were female (2). Hormonal imbalance and physiological changes as a result indicate two periods most vulnerable to the development and progression of aneurysms – pregnancy and menopause. Pregnancy is also characterized by hemodynamic physiological changes, especially pronounced in the third trimester and the term of childbirth. Fluid retention in the body causes an increase in cardiac output, by about 50% in the third trimester (2,3), caused by the development of hypertension accompanied by tachycardia, increased stress on

the wall of the blood vessel, which affects the development or enlargement of an existing aneurysm and an increased risk of rupture.

There are still no clearly criteria for deciding how to complete a pregnancy, but operational technique – cesarean section in the literature is represented with about 78% (3) in untreated aneurysms, while in operationally resolved aneurysms can safely plan vaginal delivery. From an anesthesiological point of view, there are also no clearly defined criteria, but the guiding principle in the decision is the same, avoid possible complications, rupture of the aneurysm. When it comes to untreated aneurysm, asymptomatic without significant progression in pregnancy, regional anesthesia is proposed due to the possibility of monitoring the neurological status of the pregnant woman / mother, while when it comes to symptomatic aneurysms, then there is general anesthesia and simultaneous childbirth and neurosurgical treatment postulate.

CASE REPORT

Pregnant woman 36 years old, first pregnancy was prepared for caesarean section due to the diagnosis of a basilar artery aneurysm. The diagnosis was made two years before pregnancy on NMR due to nonspecific headaches and pain in the lumbosacral spine (picture No 1) Regularly monitored by a neurosurgeon before and during pregnancy. Without neurological expression

of aneurysm during the entire period. Without significant comorbidities, during pregnancy due to tachycardia, calcium blocker therapy was introduced – Verapamil 40mg. It was suggested by neurosurgeons that the pregnancy end with a caesarean section, with the suggestion that the type of anesthesia be neuroaxial spinal anesthesia. In preoperative preparation by anesthesiologists, it was decided that the anesthesiological approach should be neuroaxial epidural anesthesia. Preoperative preparation involved the control of vital parameters and preload of the patient by infusion of crystalloid 1000ml Sol. Ringer. Epidural space was identified at the L3-4 level using the loss of resistance method and placed an epidural catheter to a depth of 8cm to reach the block level up to Th 4. After checking the position of the epidural catheter with test dose (Lidocaine 2%), a bolus dose of local anesthetic with an

adjuvant (12ml 0.5% levobupivacaine with 2ml fentanyl) was given. At the same time, an infusion of ephedrine (25mg/500ml salt) was started, with the aim of titrating the rate of infusion and thus maintaining stability without sudden variation. The newborn was of satisfactory neonatological status, APGAR 9. The patient was hemodynamically stable during cesarean section and during the first 24 hours postoperatively without any changes in general condition. Postoperative analgesia was provided via the placed epidural catheter – 6ml of 0.25% levobupivacaine with opioid adjuvant. The epidural catheter was removed 48 hours after cesarean section. During the periparturient period without the manifestation of neurological expression of the existence of an aneurysm. The patient in good general condition was discharged home on the third day.

Picture No 1 NMR aneurysm a. basilaris (aneurysm size 2.8 mm)

DISCUSSION

An intracranial aneurysm is a thinning/enlargement (fusiform aneurysms) or protrusion (saccular "berry" aneurysms) localized on the arterial blood vessels of the brain. According to various studies, it is estimated that they exist in 6% of the adult population. (3,4) The most common localization are the places where the arteries branch – locus minoris resistance. For the formation of an aneurysm, it is necessary that the wall of the blood vessel at the place of its occurrence is altered by birth or by the action of some of the harmful factors (high blood pressure, cigarette smoking, cocaine use, infections of blood vessels, female sex, altered blood stream flow . . .) (4).

Intracranial aneurysm is characterized by nonspecific symptoms (pain above and/or behind the eye, changes in vision or double vision, unilateral enlargement of the pupil, tingling of half of the face, epileptic seizures) which are most often the result of enlargement and pressure on the surrounding structures – cranial nerves. The anterior, carotid part of cerebral circulation is the most common site of localization of the aneurysm 88.64% (a. cerebri media most often affected 36.21%) versus 11.35% aneurysms of the posterior, vertebro-basilar part (Clinic for Neurosurgery KCS) (5,6). The

importance of vertebrobasilar chain aneurysms (a. basilaris) is characterized by the progressive development of the mass effect in the enlargement of the aneurysm. Aneurysm size and risk for rupture – intracranial hemorrhage are not correlated, Raps et al reported 7 patients with symptomatic aneurysms less than 10mm, Przelomski showed 10 patients, while Račić et al reported 8 patients (7). The third trimester and childbirth itself are the periods of greatest risk for ruptures of the existing aneurysm, in relation to hemodynamic changes. This affects the obstetric decision for the operative termination of pregnancy. During the first 8th week of pregnancy there is an increase in cardiac output by about 20% while the maximum increase of about 60% is expected around the 28th week of pregnancy. In addition to this vasodilation of peripheral blood vessels and lowering peripheral vascular resistance is observed with about 25-30% (7) and is another factor of hemodynamic changes. During childbirth, there is a significant increase in cardiac output by about 15% in the first birth ingenuity even by about 50% in the second birth ingenuity, which is a consequence of the body's response to pain and excitement, sympathetic stimulation – an increase in pressure and pulse. (3,4,7)

The anesthesiological approach to a pregnant woman with a diagnosed aneurysm is directly dependent on physiological hemodynamic and hormonal changes in pregnancy, there are still no clearly defined criteria for choosing the type of anesthesia, but neuroaxial anesthesia stands out because of the possibility of monitoring the neurological status of the patient during labor. Another significant advantage is bypassing sudden hemodynamic variations during general anesthesia. Induction to anesthesia is characterized by the influence of drugs – hypnotics, muscle relaxants. Ensuring the airway – intubation is accompanied by a sudden jump in pressure and pulse and special importance is placed on the known risk of the scenario of difficult airways in pregnant women, the risk of aspiration – a full stomach (8,9,10). According to available data, the risk of aneurysm rupture during the induction to anesthesia ranges from 0.5-2% (2) with a mortality rate of 75%. For the purpose of simultaneous obstetric and neurosurgical work, general anesthesia is chosen, but even then the most important emphasis is on hemodynamic, uteroplacental and intracranial stability. In these patients, the suggestion is to avoid the administration of mannitol and osmotic diuretics until the completion of obstetric work in order to maintain good uteroplacental circulation and avoid dehydration and hypernatremia of the newborn, after obstetric work neurosurgically guided by the basic postulates of maternity care(5). Neuroaxial anesthesia, spinal block, according to literature data, had a slight advantage over the epidural block, as a factor of decision emphasized the technique and speed of the performed block, i. e. the risk of accidental puncture of the dura when performing the epidural block with a wide Tuohy needle and consequently a sudden variation of the intracranial and cerebral perfusion pressure. While a significant advantage of epidural block is better hemodynamic stability and the absence of sudden variations in hemodynamics after giving local anesthetic, less pronounced nausea and urge to vomit thus less strain of the patient, as well as early rapid mobilization without the need for 24 hours bed rest after childbirth. In our review, we showed another significant advantage, the ability to place an epidural catheter and provide prolonged postoperative pain control and thus maintain hemodynamic stability in the first 48 hours, which are considered the highest risk period when pain can be a significant provoking factor.

When deciding on epidural block as the choice of anesthesia, block safety is a very important factor that entails the experience of performing an epidural block in pregnant women without comorbidities, then impeccable and safe checking of motor and sensory block and giving enough time to achieve adequate block before starting operational work. After the birth of the baby, it can be start continuous infusion of remifentanyl on the syringe pump (ml/h or TCI) to achieve adjuvant analgesia. (11,12) According to some studies there is a possibility of using adjuvant short-term doses of remifentanyl infusion until the incision on the uterus when stopping the infusion is necessary to prevent respiratory depression of the newborn.

The progress of radiological examinations and their wider representation in the general population

made it possible to detect many more patients of the generative period with the existence of aneurysms. There are still no official data on the incidence and prevalence of these patients, but the anesthesiological approach is directly related to the fact that anesthesia and surgical treatment can be the moment of manifestation of the first symptoms, and at the same time the complications of the existence of unruptured asymptomatic aneurysms.

CONCLUSION

The choice of anesthesia management is based on the safety and security of the patient during the perioperative period. It requires a good plan and consideration of all parameters during decision-making. This is especially important in obstetrics with an emphasis on high-risk pregnancies, because there is always the care of at least two lives, mother and newborn. Intracranial aneurysm in pregnancy is a major challenge and requires multidisciplinary in the approach with respect to the postulates of hemodynamic, uteroplacental and intracranial stability of the patient. Insufficient number of papers on this topic and defining clear recommendations are an aggravating circumstance and therefore each new patient brings some new knowledge and experience. Our conclusion is that epidural anesthesia in the safe hands of an experienced anesthesiologist is the best choice for caesarean section.

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